

PATTERN LANGUAGE: IDENTIFICATION OF DESIGN OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE CHILD WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER (ASD) TO DEVELOP HIS/HER SOCIAL SKILLS.

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ABSTRACT

Children with ASDs (Autism Spectrum Disorders) have different cognitive disorders. Social interaction is the most discussed area that they fail to establish and develop. Social skills help the child to establish his/her social interaction. In order to teach social skills to children with ASDs, they should be emotionally engaged in the process of teaching. In this research, set of Patterns – based on Christopher Alexander’s Pattern Language - are proposed that could help to understand what emotionally engaging design opportunities exist for teaching social skills to the children with ASDs at the early preschool ages (2 to 5). These social skills and related issues are discussed in the proposed patterns: Communication of Needs and Ideas, Joint Attention, Entry/Approach Skills, Eye Contact, Maintenance Skills, Play, Social Interaction, and Emotional Expression. Patterns with uniform structure and format were developed based on the literature review, informal observations, discussion sessions with parents and instructors of children with ASDs, and industrial design perspective.

Keywords: ASDs (Autism Spectrum Disorders), Industrial Design, Social Interaction, Pattern Language, Social Skills.

INTRODUCTION

Children with ASDs (Autism Spectrum Disorders) have different cognitive disorders. Social interaction is the most discussed area that they fail to establish and develop (Shapiro and Accardo, 2008). Social skills help the child to establish his/her social interaction. Emotionally enhanced engaging instructional tools can help children with ASDs to learn social skills that

could help them with their social interaction with parents, friends, and instructors in their future social lives. And it also helps to save the cost and time invested by the educational systems and the parents of the children with ASDs.

The research proposed is qualitative and exploratory. A literature review and informal observations helped to establish the first draft of patterns based on the Pattern Language that were used for the discussion sessions. Pattern Language is a structured method of describing good design practices within a field of expertise (Alexander et al., 1977). People of ordinary intelligence can use this design approach to successfully solve very large, complex design problems (for this research, identification of design opportunities that could help parents and instructors to teach social skills to children with ASDs). Eight patterns were identified and developed consisting of problems and solutions for each of five social skills and three related issues. A social skill is any skill facilitating interaction and communication with others (National Association of School Psychologists). The social skills are Communication of Needs and Ideas, Entry/Approach Skills, Joint Attention, Eye Contact, and Maintenance Skills. And the three related areas are Social Interaction, Emotional Expression and Play. All these eight social skills and related issues were considered through the industrial design perspective (creating design solutions) and within the pattern language structure.

Discussion sessions – conducted in five sessions with six participants – helped to refine and redefine some of the design opportunities and problems in the patterns. Eight proposed patterns – along with

recommendations and guidelines – are the final outcome of the research.

AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASDs) are characterized by impaired social interaction and communication, and by restricted and repetitive behavior. In U.S. 1 percent of the children ages 3-17 have ASDs. It is the fastest-growing developmental disability with about 1% growth rate and 10 - 17 % annual growth. There is \$60 billion annual cost with 60% of costs in adult services (National Children's Health Survey, 2009). Failure to establish typical social interactions is one of the major issues for children with ASDs at early ages. Different elements of qualitative impairment in social interaction are considered as diagnostic criteria for autistic disorder (Shapiro & Accardo, 2008, p.3):

- Marked impairment in the use of multiple nonverbal behaviors such as eye-to-eye gaze, facial expression, body postures, and gestures to regulate social interaction.
- Failure to develop peer relationships appropriate to developmental level.
- A lack of spontaneous seeking to share enjoyment, interests, or achievements with other people (e.g., a lack of showing, bringing, or pointing out objects of interest).
- A lack of social or emotional reciprocity. Children with ASDs have pervasive disability to establish and maintain age-typical relationships, particularly with peers, preventing successful social engagement (Shapiro & Accardo, 2008, p.139).

Two of the main characteristics of Autism Spectrum Disorders are:

- Delayed or impaired social skills.
- Impairment in functional communication.

Within the domain of socialization, behaviors of interest include a lack of peer relationships; impairments in nonverbal behaviors to communicate and regulate social interaction, such as the use of eye contact and facial expression; impaired shared attention with others. (Shapiro & Accardo, 2008, p.191).

PATTERN LANGUAGE

In the first volume of his central work, *The Timeless Way of Building* (Alexander, 1979), architect Christopher Alexander argues that buildings and towns that people enjoy living in have a certain, timeless "quality without a name" that cannot be reduced to a single dimension. Instead, he proposed that the design of these environments has succeeded in supporting the "patterns of events" that frequently happen there, by implementing a number of according geometric patterns, or relationships between their spatial constituents (Borchers, 2001, p. 11).

This is how the very first pattern language was established. The elements of this language are entities called "patterns". Each pattern describes a problem which occurs over and over again in our environment, and then describes the core of the solution to that problem, in such a way that you can use this solution a million times over, without ever doing it the same way twice (Alexander et al., 1977, p. x). These patterns generally solve a problem of conflicting "forces" or interests. These can also be of a social, economic, natural and physical nature.

Patterns are not isolated: they refer to the other, smaller scale patterns for the solution they describe, and they can only be used in a certain type of context, which is the result of applying larger-scale patterns. This structure links patterns together to form a hierarchical pattern language for the design of a certain building, and further to a language for the design of a whole town. Patterns are iteratively magnified, fixed, and improved (Borchers, 2001, p. 11-12). A central property of patterns is their uniform structure and format. Each of Alexander's patterns consists of the same types of components, presented in the same sequence and form:

- The *name* of the pattern,
- A *ranking* of its validity,
- A *picture* as an example of its application,
- The *context* in which it is to be used,
- A short *problem statement*,
- A more detailed *problem description* with empirical background,

- The central *solution* of the pattern,
- A *diagram* illustrating the solution,
- And finally *references* to smaller patterns.

Name, ranking, and context create the introductory part of each pattern. Problem statement, problem description, (design) solutions and diagrams (Sketches) (Borchers, 2001, p. 18). According to cognitive theory, patterns might be a particularly effective way to organize complex information (Barsalou, 1992). Patterns in a broader sense can be found in architecture, organizational behavior, history of science and even basic text writing (Borchers, 2001, p. 44). Several others have noticed the potential of pattern languages for interdisciplinary design. Denning and Dargen (1996), for example, suggest a technique called Pattern Mappings as a basis for cross-disciplinary software design. Granlund and Lafreniere (1999) use patterns to describe business domains, processes, and tasks.

IDENTIFICATION AND FRAMEWORK OF DESIGN OPPORTUNITIES: PATTERNS FOR THE SOCIAL SKILLS OF CHILDREN WITH ASDS

This research intends to provide a new perspective on defining, analyzing, and refining existing problems and developing solutions for the social skills of children with ASDs. Industrial design perspective could provide opportunities for the parents and instructors of the children with ASDs to challenge the existing issues related to the social skills (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of design issues around social interaction.

The conception of a design is not simply a representation in visual form of predetermined values, but a creative, catalytic process in which external factors interact with the beliefs, talents and skills of

individual designers or design-groups. The influence of external factors is generally greatest in establishing parameters for the utilitarian function of design – that is, the criteria by which it will be judged suitable for an intended working purpose. Individual creativity is predominant in determining the extent to which the resulting form offers aesthetic experience and has a psychological or symbolic function (Heskett, 1984, p. 8). As Heskett states in his book, industrial design results in creative solutions for the psychological or symbolic functions. When practiced with a participatory mindset, industrial design can provide design solutions for parents and instructors of children with ASDs. It also provides a different perspective allowing parents and instructors or therapists and experts to communicate issues and design solutions around social skills for children with ASDs.

In this study, pattern language helped to structure ideas around social skills. It helped to organize and prioritize ideas for each social skill and three other related issues. It provided steps of the process from problem to the solution: title, problem description, solutions and relationships of the whole process (each pattern) to the others. It also helped in analysis and organization of complicated inter-relationships between the social skills and related issues. For example, “Eye Contact” skill is important to “Joint Attention” and “Play” can be a joyful experience for the child while he/she is learning the skills. Pattern Language helped the parents and instructors to communicate ideas, solutions, and problems of social skills of children with ASDs. The Patterns were used in the discussion sessions (Figure 2) with the parents and instructors and were helpful in allowing the participants to more readily contribute ideas and identify issues.

OBJECTIVES

Identification of problems of social skills for the children with ASDs was the first goal of the research leading to the identification of design opportunities. Identification of emotionally engaging design opportunities was followed by understanding and suggesting how form, color, and the function of tools, toys and devices used in the ASD interventions, could be emotionally more engaging and be supported with visually motivating ideas. Communication of these

ideas also was a challenge. Unique form and structure of the Pattern Language helped to reach the format that could communicate ideas, problems and solutions with parents and instructors. At one level, patterns were used with parents and instructors to discuss social skills issues. Later the patterns were revised and refined to serve as the final outcome of this study meeting all three of the following objectives:

- Identify emotionally engaging design opportunities that could help parents and instructors to teach social skills to the children with ASDs.
- Suggest complementary and supportive “design opportunities” from the industrial design perspective, and provide a possible design tool for the industrial designer who would be interested in this subject.
- Communicate “design opportunities” and “situations” for teaching social skills to the children with ASDs by the help of pattern language structure.

TARGET USERS

Parents/caregivers, instructors, therapists and experts are the target users; and generally anyone who is involved in the area of teaching social skills to children with ASDs could benefit from using the outcome of this research (such as designers). Social skills of the children at the early ages (preschoolers from 2 to 5 years old) are discussed in the patterns.

METHODS

The literature review was helpful in the understanding of the topic of “autism”, the learning contexts for the children with ASDs, and existing ASD projects. Several informal observations were conducted in the special preschool classes at Nisonger Center at The Ohio State University (founded in 1966, among the first group of federally funded University Centers for Excellence in Developmental Disabilities and widely respected for its interdisciplinary research, education and clinical services). Unobtrusive observation was conducted, i.e. a method for studying behavior in which the individuals do not know they are being observed (Lee, 2000, p.1). The informal observations

were complemented with discussions with instructors of the special preschool classes. Discussion sessions with parents and instructors of children with ASDs were the main method used for this research. Preliminary patterns (Figure 2) were discussed in the discussion sessions.

INFORMAL OBSERVATION

Children with ASDs were observed at the special preschool classes at Nisonger Center during the months of March, April, May and June 2011. It provided a chance to observe children in the real environment where they interact with others, learn and use social skills.

DISCUSSION SESSIONS

Discussion sessions were conducted with 6 participants. Discussion sessions were 45 to 60 minutes long and they were conducted in 5 sessions. In each session the social skills for the children with ASDs were discussed. Participants were presented with eight sheets of patterns (i.e. the eight patterns in draft form in Figure 2) and they commented on and discussed each of those patterns.

Participants

Six participants attended the sessions. Three of the participants were parents and three of them were instructors of the 3 to 5 years old children with ASDs.

Figure 2. The eight preliminary patterns.

DATA ANALYSIS

Participants were coded X1-6. Discussion sessions were audio recorded and transcribed. Transcripts of the discussion sessions were reviewed iteratively to identify the concepts and ideas (informing design

solutions and problems in proposed patterns) for each pattern against the established objectives of the research. Transcripts were broken down into the main ideas of each participant in separate tables for each pattern that helped to refine and revise the design opportunities. These ideas were reflected in the proposed patterns (Figure 3). A set of guidelines and recommendations for the social skills were suggested (in twelve action statements) that helped to structure and inform each of the proposed patterns (Figure 4).

RESULTS: PROPOSED PATTERNS

Figure 3. Proposed Patterns

Proposed patterns were refined based on the researcher’s reflection and interpretation of the issues around social skills, industrial design perspective, literature review, and informal observations. The proposed patterns also reflect the ideas, comments and concerns of the parents, sibling, and instructors of the children with ASDs who participated in the discussion sessions.

Figure 4. Annotated proposed pattern of Emotional Expression consists of the following sections: title of pattern, introductory image, relationships of given pattern with other patterns, situation (problems), design opportunities (solutions), and sketches for the solutions.

CONCLUSION

Each of the proposed patterns (Figure 4) could be used by parents and instructors of the children with ASDs. Instructors could refer to these patterns when teaching social skills to the children with ASDs in class. And also they could use the components of patterns to communicate problems and solutions of social skills with parents. Patterns could provide parents with ideas about how they could improve their children’s social skills.

Most of the methods and techniques being used in the classroom setting by the instructor and at home by the parents for teaching social skills to children with ASDs are based on eclectic principles and individualized to each child with ASD. Solutions for helping children with ASDs to develop their social skills are mostly based on one-to-one sessions with repeated trials of the preferred behavior and they lack emotional

engagement. Ways of teaching social skills are unique for each child with ASD, but parents and instructors participated in the research all emphasized on more colorful, interesting, multi-sensorial solutions and this is where industrial design – as an interdisciplinary field capable of providing creative and emotionally engaging solutions based on form, color, and function – could help parents and instructors to teach social skills.

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